

Municipal Policies to support youth and retain young populations

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Welcome to Armamar!

It's a great pleasure to receive you here, in the Interpretative Centre of Douro Women. A space bringing a new life, every day, to the emblematic building of the old Wine Cooperative of Armamar. Opening doors to the development of the municipality and the critical spirit on matters of human rights, gender equality and female identity.

Land of wine and apples, Armamar is known as the land of emotions. It shares its territory with the Douro Valley to the north and the Beira plateau to the south. It is a municipality rich in traditions, culture, typical cuisine, and natural and built heritage. But above all, the most valuable thing is our people.

Armamar is a municipality located in the interior of Portugal, with a low population density. Many young people, unfortunately, are forced to leave in search of better living conditions. We cannot allow this to continue happening with such intensity.

No community can think about its future without being committed to the present of its youth. Young people are agents of transformation — they carry within them the energy, ideas, and creativity that drive progress.

That is why municipal youth support policies need to be strategic and comprehensive. In the case of the Municipality of Armamar, youth policies are implemented to ensure access to quality education, create opportunities for skills development, promote entry into the job market, ensure access to culture, encourage sports participation, and provide spaces for social engagement.

It is essential to listen to young people. With that in mind, we established the Municipal Youth Council to involve them in decision-making processes - whether in infrastructure investment, entrepreneurship, the stimulation of the local economy, or in areas such as communication and mobility solutions, access to housing, and even leisure opportunities. *“Keeping young people in their birthplace also means preserving local identity and strengthening community ties.”*

In this process of investing in youth policies, it is essential to ensure sustainable development and innovation within the region. This means fostering growth while respecting natural resources, valuing local culture, and ensuring social inclusion—with a focus on quality of life for all, including benefits for future generations.

Investing in projects such as ARMA-Sci (Armamar's Scientific Capital Promotion Network) allows us to combine development and innovation, ensuring effectiveness through the contribution of technical and scientific knowledge to all areas - such as agriculture, tourism, education, health, and more - by identifying the most suitable problems and solutions for our reality.

We are very pleased with this network of partnerships between the municipality, the science promotion association, the school group, universities, entrepreneurs, and civil society. It enables us all to foster this ecosystem of innovation and development - full of possibilities - where young people are the main targets.

Public administration can act as a facilitator among these actors, promoting spaces for cooperation, local agreements, and consortia that enhance sustainable and innovative actions. It is through this collaboration that robust solutions emerge, policies become more effective, and long-lasting impacts are achieved.

Thanks for your attention!